

Synthesis of some New Derivatives of Pyrazolin-5-ones

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Two series of pyrazolin-5-ones have been synthesised by the reaction of ethyl 2-phenylhydrazono-3-oxobutyrate with the antitubercular drug isoniazid and with the antihypertensive drug hydrallazine respectively. The structures of the compounds of both the series have been established on the basis of elemental analyses and spectral data.

PYRAZOLIN-5-one and its derivatives are biologically active compounds¹ and also find applications in photography² and as dye³. Furthermore, isoniazid⁴ and hydrallazine⁵ are well-known drugs and it is well accepted that incorporation of hydrazono group enhances the biological activity of heterocycles. In view of the biological importance of hydrazono group^{6,7}, pyrazolin-5-ones, hydrallazine and isoniazid, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise some of these compounds as possible biologically active compounds.

In the present investigation the following two series of pyrazolin-5-ones were synthesised. Compounds of series-I was synthesised by the reaction of ethyl 2-phenylhydrazono-3-oxobutyrate with isoniazid whereas compounds of series-II were

synthesised by the reaction of ethyl 2-phenylhydrazono-3-oxobutyrate with hydrallazine (Scheme 1). The structures of the compounds have been established on the basis of elemental analyses and spectral data. The reactivity of ethyl 2-phenylhydrazono-3-oxobutyrate was smooth and the products were obtained in good yields.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (CH₃OH) on a Specord Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer, and pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Perkin-Elmer R-35 using tetramethyl silane as an internal standard. All the melting points are uncorrected. Compounds were routinely checked for their purity on silica gel-G plates.

1-Isonicotinoyl-3-methyl-4-(phenylhydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (1): To ethyl 2-phenylhydrazono-3-oxobutyrate⁸ (0.002 mol) dissolved in acetic acid (10–15 ml) was added a solution of isoniazid (0.002 mol) in acetic acid (15–20 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight. On cooling, the resulting, shining crystals of **1** was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, (70%), m.p. 45° (Found: C, 74.30; H, 2.70; N, 5.21. C₁₆H₁₅N₅O₂ calcd. for: C, 74.50; H, 2.88; N, 5.52%); λ_{max} 245 and 395 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 240 (NH), 1 730 (exocyclic CO), 1 640 (conjugated CO), 1 520 (NH–N=C) and 750 cm⁻¹ (substituted phenyl); δ(DMSO-d₆) 2.7 (3H, CH₃), 7.8–8.4 (substituted phenyl) and 11.2 (H, NH). Similarly, other derivatives were prepared by taking suitably substituted ethyl 2-phenylhydrazono-3-oxobutyrate (Table 1).

3-Methyl-4-(phenylhydrazono)-1-phthalazyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (2): To ethyl 2-phenylhydrazono-3-oxobutyrate (0.003 mol) dissolved in acetic acid (10–15 ml) was added a solution of hydrallazine (0.003 mol) in acetic acid (15–20 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stand overnight. On cooling,

Scheme 1

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1 AND 2*

Compd. no	R	M.p. °C	Colour	Yield %	Mol. formula
1a	H	45	Light yellow	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₂
1b	2-Cl	200	Lemon yellow	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₅ O ₂ Cl
1c	3-Cl	120	Orange	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₅ O ₂ Cl
1d	4-Cl	70	Yellow	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₅ O ₂ Cl
1e	2-CH ₃	165	Yellow	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂
1f	3-CH ₃	55	Yellow	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂
1g	4-CH ₃	85	Yellow	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂
1h	2-OCH ₃	165	Dark yellow	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂
1i	4-OCH ₃	165	Yellow	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂
1j	2-OC ₂ H ₅	185	Yellow	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₂
1k	2-NO ₂	160	Dark yellow	62	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₆ O ₄
1l	3-NO ₂	280	Brown	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₆ O ₄
1m	4-NO ₂	198	Light yellow	62	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₆ O ₄
1n	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	80	Brown	70	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₂
1o	2,5-(Cl) ₂	120	Brown yellow	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₅ O ₂ Cl ₂
1p	4-NH ₂ , 2-NO ₂	75	Yellow	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₇ O ₄
1q	2-(COOH) ₂	225	Yellow	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄
1r	4-OH	80	Yellow	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃
2a	H	50	Orange	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₆ O
2b	2-Cl	50	Light brown	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₆ OCl
2c	3-Cl	65	Light yellow	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₆ OCl
2d	4-Cl	50	Mud yellow	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₆ OCl
2e	2-CH ₃	80	Yellow	50	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₆ O
2f	4-CH ₃	80	Light yellow	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₆ O
2g	2-OCH ₃	60	Black	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₆ O ₂
2h	3-OCH ₃	45	Yellow	70	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₆ O ₂
2i	4-OCH ₃	60	Yellow	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₆ O ₂
2j	2-OC ₂ H ₅	70	Yellow	75	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₂
2k	2-NO ₂	70	Brown	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₇ O
2l	3-NO ₂	160	Yellow	50	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₇ O
2m	4-NO ₂	45	Light yellow	55	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₇ O
2n	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	80	Brown	65	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₆ O
2o	2,5-(Cl) ₂	70	Yellow	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₆ OCl ₂
2p	4-NH ₂ , 2-NO ₂	86	Yellow	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₂
2q	2-(COOH) ₂	120	Yellow	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₃
2r	4-OH	140	Orange	70	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₃

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

the resulting sticky product was dissolved in water-ether mixture. From this mixture it was extracted by solvent ether, (55%), m.p. 50° (Found: C, 62.1; H, 4.2; N, 24.10. C₁₈H₁₄N₆O. calcd. for: C, 62.4; H, 4.0; N, 24.27%); λ_{max} (CH₃OH) 235 and 380 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 240 (NH), 1 635 (conjugated CO), 1 510 (NH-N=C) and 750 cm⁻¹ (substituted phenyl); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.4 (3H, CH₃), 7.5-8.3 (substituted phenyl) and 10.6 (H, NH).

Similarly, other derivatives were synthesised by taking appropriate substituted ethyl 2-phenylhydrazono-3-oxobutylate (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

The structure of the compounds (Table 1) have been established on the basis of elemental and spectral analysis. Perusal of spectral data revealed that these compounds exist in hydrazono form (structures 1 and 2) rather than in any of the three conceivable.

The ir band at 3 240 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to NH group (hydrogen bonded) as in α-phenylhydrazonoketones, which is present only in structures 1, 2. Similarly structures 1 and 2 require that the C=O group in 5-position should be in conjugation with the -C=N- group. Two strong bands appear at 1 730 (exocyclic C=O) and 1 640 cm⁻¹ (conjugated C=O cyclic). The presence of low frequency bands in compounds under investigation can therefore be attributed to the conjugation of cyclic C=O group in position-5 with the -C=N group. Tanner⁶ also attributed the appearance of C=O band at lower frequency for 3-phenylhydrazono-2,4-dione to conjugation of C=O group with -C=N group. Furthermore, lower carbonyl band may also be assigned to C=O group in position-5 due to its participation in intramolecular hydrogen bonding with NH group. Hydrazono structure (1, 2) is further supported by nmr spectral studies. The nmr spectra exhibit a signal at δ 11.2 ppm which could be assigned to the hydrogen bonded NH grouping. Thus on the basis of ir and nmr spectral data it can be concluded that these compounds exist in hydrazono (1, 2) form.

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